

Histology of the Adrenal Gland of Emu (*Dromaius novaehollandiae*)

N. Rajendranath¹, A. Prasanth Babu, P. Jagapathi Ramayya, H.S. Patki and
T.S. Chandrasekhara Rao

Department of Veterinary Anatomy, College of Veterinary Science, Sri Venkateswara Veterinary University,
Tirupati 517502, Andhra Pradesh

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Extensive information on histological aspect of the adrenal gland of domestic fowl (Hodges, 1974), Geese and Duck (Hassan, 1975) and Japanese quail (Sabiha *et al.*, 2004) is available. Information on the histology of the same in emu is sparse. Hence an attempt was made to record the histological details of the adrenal gland of emu.

Materials and Methods

Six adult emu birds irrespective of the sex and age were utilized for the present study. The birds were slaughtered for commercial purpose at Golden emu farm, Medak. The tissue pieces were collected from the adrenal gland and were processed for paraffin sections of 5-6m thickness. The sections were subjected to routine Haematoxylin and Eosin staining as well as special staining methods like Vangieson's method for collagen fibers (Singh and Sulochana, 1997).

Results and Discussion

The adrenal gland was covered by a thin capsule consisting of approximately an equal number of collagen and elastic fibers interspersed with large number of fibroblasts. Just below the capsule large number of capillaries and veins were observed. The adrenal parenchyma was composed of two main tissue types i.e., cortex or inter renal tissue and medulla or chromaffin tissue. The cortical and medullary tissues were intimately mixed together throughout the gland.

The proportion of the cortical tissue was more than the medullary tissue in the adrenal

gland of emu, Sabiha *et al.*, (*loc.cit*) reported that the proportion of corticomedullary tissue varied among the age groups and sex. Oakberg (1951) reported that cortex and medulla showed approximately equal proportions in all the regions of the gland in fowl. The cortical cords were packed by the reticular fibers and elastic fibers. Between the cortical and medullary tissue sinusoids were present and they were lined by elongated endothelial cells.

The cortical tissue was arranged as irregular cords and intermingled with medullary tissue. The cortical tissue was clearly demarcated into a peripheral subcapsular zone and a central inner zone as in fowl (Unsicker, 1973) and geese and duck (Hassan, *loc.cit*). The Peripheral subcapsular zone of cortex consisted of radially arranged cords, they formed loops against the

Fig 1: Photomicrograph of adrenal gland showing Capsule (C); Cortex (COR); Medulla (MED); Sub capsular zone (SC); Central zone (CZ); Sinusoids(S). H&E x 100

¹Corresponding author : Email : nrjnath@gmail.com

Fig 2: Photomicrograph of adrenal gland showing Cortex (cor) and Medulla (med). H&E x 100

Fig 3: Photomicrograph of adrenal gland showing Cortex (cor); Medulla (med). Gridley's reticular method x 400

capsule, whereas in the central zone of the cortex the cords were large but they were not in regular pattern. Hassan (*loc.cit*) in geese and duck and Sabiha *et al.*, (*loc.cit*) had noted type 1, 2, 3, 4 cells in cortex of Japanese quail. But in the present study such type of cells were not identified.

The cells of the subcapsular zone of the cortex were large columnar with nucleus and dense granular cytoplasm. The nucleolus was placed in the middle and pyknotic changes were observed in some cells. The cells as well as nuclei of the central zone were smaller and columnar type. They were densely arranged compared to the cells of subcapsular zone.

The medullary cells were arranged as clumps or irregular masses of cells. These clumps were smaller in the subcapsular zone of cortex and larger in the central zone. Medullary cells were polygonal in shape and larger than the cortical cells. The cytoplasm of these cells was basophilic due to numerous basophilic chromaffin granules. A centrally placed nucleus with one or two nucleoli was observed as described by Sivaram (1965) in fowl. Fine nerve plexuses and ganglionic cells between the medullary cells were observed. These nerve plexuses were also noted between the cortical cords of the adrenal gland of emu.

Summary

The adrenal gland of emu was covered by a thin capsule consisting of approximately equal numbers of collagen and elastic fibres. The adrenal parenchyma was composed of cortex or inter-renal tissue and medullary or chromaffin tissue. The cortex consisted of sub-capsular and central zones. The cells in these zones were columnar type and showed eosinophilic cytoplasm. The cells in the medulla were polygonal in shape contained basophilic cytoplasm and arranged as clumps in between the cortical tissue. Nerve fibers and ganglions were observed in the medullary tissue. These nerve plexuses were also noted between the cortical cords of the adrenal gland of emu.

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